

CECOMEC project report

Year 1

Overview.

During the first year the main activity of the CECOMEC project [Dacapito, F., Bochentyn, B., & Korecki, P. (2024). Tuning CEria-based COMpounds as effective catalyst for Electrochemical Cells. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14578906>] has been the recruitment of the post doc scientist. This has been achieved through two calls, only the second of which permitted to hire a candidate. At the end of the year the candidate entered in operation and the activity of the project has started.

Recruitment procedure.

The first call was launched on Feb 9th and the meeting of the first selection took place on March 22th. Four applicants were selected for the interview and, in the subsequent meeting on Apr 9th, one candidate was selected. Eventually this candidate declined our offer, and the procedure had to be repeated. The new call was opened on June 19th and the first meeting was hold on July 8th with the admission of two applicants to the interview. The second meeting was hold on July 24th and the final candidate was selected. Dr Simone Amatori accepted the contract and he started working for the project on November 1st.

Activity at LISA

Dr Amatori has started learning the details of the beamline software and data collection procedures. He has also been instructed on how to carry out structural simulations with the code VASP. He is already familiar with the common codes for EXAFS data extraction and analysis. A first batch of samples from Gdansk has been received and he is now planning how to prepare them for the measurement.

Planning 2025

For next year it is planned a first experimental session at the LISA beamline focused on the samples received. Simone will spent February in Gdansk preparing a new batch of samples that will be analyzed at LISA soon after and then at SOLARIS at the end of March.

Figure 1: Plan of the activities in the first quarter 2025.